

2.1 Value Delivery Planning [categorized under Principle 2: Plan and deliver software frequently]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods, techniques and tools for planning the delivery of value by means of realized user stories, epics or features.

Examples for investigated aspects: Release planning, Work package estimation, Collaborative planning, Backlog management, User stories

1. Does this cluster fit well within the principle it is categorized under?

Fits very well Fits well Neither & Nor Does not Fit well Very Unfit

1.2 This cluster fits better within the following principle(s)

- Embrace Change to Deliver Customer Value
- Plan and Deliver Software Frequently
- Human Centricity
- Technical Excellence
- Customer Collaboration
- None
- Other : _____

2. Please rate the degree to which this cluster is ***important*** with respect to the organizational scale.

- For the 3rd and higher Level Units (bottom-up e.g., Project Level or Solution Train Level), this cluster is:

Very important Important Neither & Nor Unimportant Very Unimportant Don't know

- For the 2nd Level Unit (bottom-up e.g., Product Level (Release Train Level), this cluster is:

Very important Important Neither & Nor Unimportant Very Unimportant Don't know

- For the 1st Level Unit (bottom-up e.g., Team level), this cluster is:

Very important Important Neither & Nor Unimportant Very Unimportant Don't know

3. Do you think this cluster should be split into or merged with multiple clusters?
(If yes, how would you name the split entities?)

Descriptive text

Exemplary aspects

Structural validation

Scale

Structural validation